

CPEC'S SOCIOECONOMIC EFFECTS ON PAKISTAN: THE DRAWBACKS OF THE PROJECT'S

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ABSTRACT

One of the main initiatives of the China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), is the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC), which includes substantial investments in infrastructure development, special economic zones, and energy projects. Despite being heralded as a game-changer for Pakistan, CPEC's detrimental socioeconomic effects have drawn serious criticism. In order to determine these effects and pinpoint any research gaps that have not yet been addressed, this study sheds light on an extensive literature evaluation. This research reveals that CPEC exacerbates already existing socioeconomic disparities, uproots local communities, degrades the environment, and raises questions about the debt sustainability of Pakistan. In this research I have evaluated the exacerbated by the lack of transparency in project execution. I have explored labor rights and wages conditions, environmental implications, and the experiences of Aboriginal communities and gendered repercussions in this article. Given that the research is still ongoing, as time goes on, more problems may arise over time. Policymakers may better grasp the possible effects on CPEC and create plans to mitigate any adverse effects that might endanger Pakistan's economy, environment, and society by carrying out more thorough study.

Keywords: CPEC, BRI, Investment opportunities, Negative Impacts, Environmental degradation, Economic disparity.

INTRODUCTION

An estimated \$62 billion would be invested in CPEC, a flagship project under China's BRI (Elmali, 2024). The initiative intends to strengthen Pakistan's economy and improve regional connections, with a primary focus on energy projects, infrastructure development, and Special Economic Zones (SEZs) (Ellahi, 2025). Although this study looks at these possible advantages, it is impossible to ignore CPEC's drawbacks. Hence, by performing a thorough literature analysis and identifying knowledge gaps, this study examines the detrimental socioeconomic effects of CPEC on Pakistan. This research article looks at the negative socioeconomic effects of CPEC on Pakistan by doing a thorough literature analysis

and identifying gaps in the available research. While this paper explores these potential benefits, it is impossible to ignore the negative effects of CPEC. As a flagship project, CPEC has been extensively studied, with numerous studies concentrating on the project's potential advantages and disadvantages. Several studies have already brought attention to the project's lack of openness, and some experts and scholars have questioned the Chinese government's involvement in the project. A report by the International Monetary Fund (IMF) claims that because of the project's lack of transparency, there are numerous worries regarding the sustainability of debt and the quality of infrastructure projects.

The environmental issues of CPEC have been clarified by a several studies. The project may negatively impact the environment, particularly where roads and other infrastructure are located. Because efforts of this nature necessitate widespread deforestation. Take Gwadar and the Karakoram Highway, for example. The purpose of the study is to draw attention to the project's potential risks. Such as biodiversity loss, habitat loss, and climate change. In addition, the project's relocation of native communities is a significant worry. Thousands of people have been displaced by the project in Baluchistan and other regions of Pakistan, according to the Centre for Social Justice (CSJ). The region's socioeconomic area has been impacted by this displacement, which has led to the loss of livelihoods.

Even though scholar have done a lot of research in this field to determine the project's possible advantages and disadvantages, more thorough and long-term study is required because the project is still in the planning stages. Not only that, but also need for research that evaluate the effect of the project on the human rights conditions in Pakistan.

Dependency theory has been used in this research as a lens to deeply understand the possible outcomes of the CPEC on Pakistan. Dependency Theory is a theoretical framework that examines the economic, political, and social relationships between two or more

countries, particularly between developed as core and developing periphery countries. The theory was mainly developed in the 1960s and 70s by Latin American scholars and economists, notably Fernando Henrique Cardoso, Andre Gunder Frank, and Raul Prebisch (Harriet Friedmann, 1977). This research paper investigates Dependency Theory, discussing its development and application to the CPEC.

In order to examine the detrimental socioeconomic effect of CPEC on Pakistan, this research is solely based on a thorough review of the literature, which includes official studies, policy papers, and publications. This report attempts to give a thorough explanation of the project's detrimental effects by critically analyzing previous research.

In order to fully comprehend the potential effects of the CPEC on Pakistan, dependency theory has been employed in this research as a lens. A theoretical framework known as dependency theory looks at the social, political, and economic ties that exist between two or more nations. Latin American economists and academicians, particularly Fernan do Henrique Cardoso, Rafael Prebisch, and Andre Gunder Frank, primarily developed the theory in the 1960s and 1970s (Harriet Friedmann, 1977). The development and application of dependency theory to the CPEC are covered in this work.

CPEC plans

Literature Review:

Socio Economic Disparities

A key development strategy is the CPEC, a flagship project of China BRI, which aims to build a network of roads, railroads, and pipelines to link China's northwest with Gwadar Port in southwest Pakistan (Mardell, 2020). Although the concept has greatly benefited the country, much more is still to come (Harriet Friedmann, 1977). This essay explores dependency theory, going over its history and how it has been used to address social inequality.

Economic inequality is also associated with the CPEC, particularly with regard to trade imbalances and debt. Because of CPEC projects, Pakistan's debt to China has alarmingly escalated, raising worries that it may eventually reach unaffordable levels (Arsalan, 2025). Furthermore, the trade gap has grown dramatically since the start of CPEC. Which has increased the disparity in trade between Islamabad and Beijing (Bilal Ameen, 2017).

The majority of CPEC related projects utilizing Chinese labor, which is regarding for

local people in light of job chances. Chinese companies frequently bring their own labor due to the language barrier and other considerations, which restricts local's employment options (Rana, 2022). Additionally, Pakistan is heavily dependent on Chinese laborers, missing out on local employment and skill development opportunities because its labor force lacks the necessary skills to work on CPEC projects (Adeel Ahmed, 2022).

The vast majority of the CPEC related projects are being developed in areas of Pakistan that are already regarded as developed. Such as the provinces of Sindh and Punjab, raising worries about the continued relegation of less developed areas like Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Baluchistan (Saleem, 2024). It has been said that the split of CPEC projects has exacerbated regional inequality and strengthened Pakistan's socioeconomic hierarchy.

Even though the CPEC aims to increase economic growth, the socioeconomic disparities it causes must be addressed. Actions should be taken to address the economic

imbalance with China, improve local employment capacity, and guarantee equitable project distribution among all regions. This will attest to the viability and wide distribution of CPEC's advantages.

Effect on Wages and Employment:

CPEC's effects on wages and employment are complicated. It encompasses more than just creating jobs; it also covers things like the type and calibre of work, wage levels, skill requirements, and the distinctions between domestic and foreign labor.

The disparity in employment between local Pakistani workers and Chinese laborers hired for CPEC projects is a serious worry. The influx of Chinese workers may increase productivity and competence, but it also raised questions about the lack of employment options for natives (Hassan, The disparity in employment between local Pakistani workers and Chinese laborers hired for CPEC projects is a serious worry. The influx of Chinese workers may increase productivity and competence, but it also raised questions about the lack of employment, 2024). Therefore, it is crucial to research how many jobs are going to local workers as opposed to foreign labor and how this is influencing employment rates overall in the CPEC affected regions.

Determining the kinds of employment being produced by CPEC and the skill levels that may be needed is also important. For example, CPEC initiatives in energy and infrastructure development can need for workers with more advanced abilities, which might not be readily available in the local workforce. Consequently, the local labor force is mostly reliant on Chinese workers. It restricts chances for wage development and local employment (Ramsha Saleem, 2022). For the local workers to be ready to work on their own, the Pakistani government must establish training facilities. Another important factor to consider is the wage level. Are the wages commensurate with the amount of labor necessary for the job? Is the earning of local and international workers different in any way? In order to eliminate any a socioeconomic difference between the both nations pertaining to the CPEC, it is crucial to address these kinds of concerns.

The sustainability of the jobs should also be considered by the policy makers. Is the employment generated by CPEC projects, for example, temporary? Are these positions temporary? Or do they result in long-term, economic strategies for the CPEC affected regions can be made easier with an understanding of this. All things considered, a more thorough investigation is needed to evaluate these factors and comprehend the wider effects of CPEC on wages and employment. To make sure that CPEC result in fair and sustained economic growth of Pakistan, such research will be beneficial.

Disparity in Regional Development:

As previously stated, the majority of CPEC related projects are being constructed in Pakistan's already established regions, namely Punjab and Sindh, ignoring Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Baluchistan's least developed regions. Causing a gap in regional growth when taking the CPEC's socioeconomic effects (Naubahar Sharif, 2025).

In addition to the geographical projects associated with the CPEC, the assessment of regional development disparity also considers the advantages of these projects, which are dispersed throughout the country. The advantages include access to infrastructure, healthcare, and education, as well as economic indices like income levels and poverty rates. Comparing the poverty and income levels of other regions with those of the CPEC project locations, for example, is crucial.

Furthermore, regional growth may also be impacted, either directly or indirectly. For instance, because CPEC projects are limited to certain regions, these areas may attract more workers than less developed once. In addition to workers, these thriving areas may attract the investments, which may result in a rise in internal migration, altering local demographics and exacerbating regional disparities.

To ensure a more equitable distribution of the projects, a more thorough investigation is needed to solve the problems pertaining to the regional imbalances associated with the CPEC. This can prevent the CPEC's advantages and necessary services from being distributed unfairly. Consequently, both developed and underdeveloped places will have equal chances.

Environmental Impact Assessment:

CPEC's effects on the environment are a serious worry. A thorough grasp of the project's environmental impact may be obtained via studies that offer data on environmental factors including biodiversity, deforestation rates, and air and water quality. To ensure that we are not gaining economic advantages at the expense of environmental collapse, such research can aid in halting the harm in its early phases.

Evaluation of the Environmental Impact:

The environmental implications of CPEC are noteworthy concern. The studies that provide environment related information such as air and water quality, deforestation rates, and biodiversity, can provide a comprehensive understanding of the project's environmental footprint. Such studies can help to stop the damage at early stages so that we assure that we are not getting economic benefits at the cost of environmental collapse.

Sustainability of Debt:

In addition to boosting economic prosperity, CPEC investments are significantly raising Pakistan's debt since the country lacks the necessary funds for the projects in included in the CPEC. Tracking Pakistan's debt levels, repayment capabilities, and revenue allocated to debt payment will require a more thorough investigation. This will help determine how the project would affect the country's financial stability.

Social Effects and Quality of Life:

As the infrastructure projects need widespread deforestation, CPEC has detrimental effects on Pakistani population's quality of life in addition to interfering with economic issues. To offer useful information on changes in health outcomes, availability to necessary services, and educational attainment in CPEC. Because the project aims to maximize the possible advantages compared to the negative consequences, such studies can assist us in eliminating the negative impacts that we are currently or will face in the future.

Rehabilitation and Displacement:

Certain CPEC development projects need the local community's evacuation from the areas where the projects are planned. Later, this leads to major problems for the local population in these places, including living conditions, lifestyles, and access to necessary services. Understanding the long-term effects of relocation and assessing the success of rehabilitation initiatives can be aided by a long-term research. To ensure that the initiative is not causing long-term losses for the local population, but rather long-term advantages.

Local Communities Displacement and Marginalization:

The CPEC is undoubtedly a multibillion-dollar infrastructure project that is part of China's BRI. It has the potential to significantly boost Pakistan's economic development, but as I have already stated, even positive things can have negative effects. This is the reason why local communities are being uprooted and degraded, especially in Pakistan's less developed area (Arfan Mahmood, 2022).

Many local populations have been displaced as a result of the CPEC's massive infrastructure expansion, including the building of pipelines, railroads, and roadways. Due to the purchase of land for these projects, many individuals have been compelled to move to another location without receiving fair compensation (Naubahar Sharif, 2025). For example, the construction of the Gwadar port and associated infrastructure in Baluchistan has resulted in the displacement of indigenous residents (Asad Raza Talpur, 2023). According to the Primer of Pakistan, the CPEC is entering its second phase of growth, therefore there are still a lot of projects to come. This, like it has in the past, may result in more relocation problems for the nearby towns (Arsalan, 2025). Because local workers lack the skill needed in the job market, they are unable to access the same employment market places as Chinese workers.

However, that is not the only problem; even if they learn the necessary abilities, there will still be a language barrier. Due to their inability to understand Chinese, the locals are unable to take use of the advantages associated with the CPEC projects (Asif Usman, 2019).

Additionally, the introduction of Chinese culture and language has raised concerns about

the cultural and social marginalization of local communities, particularly in underdeveloped areas like Baluchistan and Gilgit-Baltistan (Hao Lu, 2025). The CPEC, which is viewed as a game-changer for Pakistan, is causing significant concerns about the marginalization and displacement of local communities. In order to ensure equitable and sustainable development, it is critical to consider local communities needs and rights when developing policies and implementing CPEC projects.

Degradation of the Environment

The flagship projects of the BRI is the CPEC, which is expected to significantly boost Pakistan's economy. But in addition to these possible advantages, the project has also brought up serious environmental issues. Which are as follows:

Air pollution:

Air pollution is yet another significant issue related to CPEC. Since the majority of energy-intensive projects are connected to coal-fired power plants, which are an important part of the CPEC, they are also a major source of air pollution, for example Sahiwal Coal power plant and Thar Coal power plant, which effected the temperature of city. In the CPEC related locations, poor air quality brought on by carbon emissions from these power plants is leading to respiratory ailments and early deaths. Furthermore, it has an effect on climate change worldwide (Tayyaba Zainab Ali, 2023). Pakistan can profit economically and socially from the CPEC, but it is also critical to develop stronger policies to lessen the potential harm to the environment. Only then will we be able to maximize the benefits of the CPEC projects rather than suffer from their negative effects. These policies should incorporate sustainable development practices, such as through environmental impact assessments, proper waste management, and the use of renewable energy sources.

Contamination of water:

Due to the dumping of industrial waste into water bodies without proper treatment, the construction of the Gwadar Port and other CPEC related industrial projects is also causing water pollution. This has an impact on local

resident's health in addition to harming marine life (Rashida Qari, 2018).

Deforestation:

Deforestation has increased significantly as a result of the CPEC's infrastructural development, which includes pipelines, roads, and railroads. It worsens the ecosystem and contributes to climate change by destroying habitat, reducing biodiversity, and increasing greenhouse gas emission (Naubahar Sharif, 2025). For example, Gilgit-Baltistan has seen severe deforestation as a result of the Karakoram Highway's construction (Rashida Qari, 2018). Despite contributing only 0.9% of the world's carbon emissions, Pakistan is experiencing a severe environmental crisis (Muhammad Adnan, 2024).

Effect on Indigenous Communities:

The effects that CPEC would have on the local community have caused many worries. Due to the project's substantial land use requirements and resulting population shifts, neighboring communities may be disproportionately impacted. Here are a few possible drawbacks:

Limited involvement in Economic:

Although CPEC is expected to boost the economy, indigenous people could not gain equally from it. The encounter prejudice since the occupations produced by the initiative do not fit with their old methods, and they are unable to engage in the new economic activities because they lack the requisite skills.

Inadequate Participation and Consultation:

Indigenous groups often say they haven't been consulted enough and involvement in local development project decision-making processes. This lack of participation may result in decision that disrespect their needs and rights and are not in their best interests. Large-scale projects like the CPEC require sufficient research to show the possible effects they may

have on the local population. Policymakers should take precautions to reduce any harm, safeguard indigenous people's rights, and guarantee that they get an equal share of the benefits associated with the CPEC (Tegan Brock, 2021).

Cultural Destruction:

Indigenous populations may experience forced cultural dilution and erosion as a result of the inflow of Chinese laborers and newcomers. A loss of cultural legacy may result from the new innovation's dominance over the local peoples, language, habits, and behaviors.

Displacement of People:

Acquiring property is frequently necessary for infrastructure development, which may result in the uprooting of nearby populations. These displacements can disturb traditional lifestyle, divide communities from one another, and result in loss of homes and livelihoods of local people. Consequently, they are experiencing alienation in a new setting and country that is far from their homes (Sheikh Arshad, 2023).

Effect on Employment of Women:

Women have few direct job options in the majority of CPEC projects, particularly in the development and infrastructure sectors, which are dominated by men (Hassan, Socio-economics impacts of CPEC on Pakistan; the dark side of the project, 2024). As a result, CPEC's employment benefits are not gender-neutral, which might exacerbate already-existing gender gaps in the workforce. The indirect effects of CPEC on female employment, however, could be more advantages. Sectors including retail, hospitality, and textiles, where female involvement is historically stronger, may see an increase with better infrastructure and more economic activity. Greater economic prospects for women may result from an increase in employment in these industries (Wania Tahir, 2022). Leading to the empowerment of women in Pakistan.

The Degradation of Environment:

According to (Aroob Fatima, 2025) a large number of indigenous groups mostly depend

on their natural environment for their substance. The lives of these populations may be directly impacted by environmental deterioration brought on by CPEC related infrastructure and industrial growth, which may also have an influence on biodiversity, water shortages, and ecosystem loss.

Insufficient Benefits:

There are concern that the compensation offered for local resident's land acquisition or relocation may not be sufficient or equitable. Sometime the compensation is not given right away, which puts the impacted communities through even more hardship.

Implications by Gender:

Despite the fact that CPEC has generally benefited Pakistan economically, it also has the potential to alter the socioeconomic landscape of the nation in the future. The gendered effects of this economic shift, however, have not received enough attention, and it is important to comprehend how it is influencing Pakistani women. Which, according to the 2017 census, make up 49% of the overall population.

Effects on Inequality of Gender:

The potential for CPEC to worsen gender inequality is its second significant gendered effect. Pakistan, which is now rated 151st out of 153 countries in the Global Gender Gap index 2020 (Ahmed, 2019). Already has a high level of gender inequality, which might be made worse by the gender discrepancies in the benefits of CPEC. The social, economic, and political obstacles that prevent women from fully participating in the economy may not be addressed by CPEC projects if they are not planned with improved regulations and a gender perspective in mind. This might possibly exacerbate gender inequality in Pakistan.

Effect on Displacement:

As with CPEC, large infrastructure projects frequently necessitate the eviction of indigenous residents. This may have an impact on these individual's quality of life, irrespective of their gender. However, research has

demonstrated that women are frequently disproportionately affected by displacement, which increases their susceptibility and limits their access to necessary resources and services (Jai Kumar & Bing Xue, 2022). Regarding the relocation of women during the CPEC projects, better policies are needed.

Working Conditions and Labor Rights:

CPEC has the potential to revolutionize Pakistan by drawing in global investments has undergone several changes without creating jobs. With the CPEC, I hope this is not the case. The CPEC currently consists of nine zones, including SEZs and Export Processing Zone (EPZs). The country's normal labor rules do not apply to EPZs (Khan, 2025).

As we have seen in the past, policy changes are rarely a huge concern when governments and premiers change. Although the infringement of local labor rights has been covered in a few research, more thorough investigation is required. Undoubtedly, one of the main initiatives of China's BRI is the CPEC, which has the potential to revolutionize Pakistan's economic situation (Dr. Sawaira Rashid, 2023). However, Policymakers must, take a closer look at its effects on Pakistani local worker's working conditions and labor rights. The purpose of this research is to investigate how to CPEC projects affect Pakistani worker's rights, working conditions, and quality of life.

Rights of Workers under CPEC:

Although CPEC is anticipated to create a large number of job possibilities for China and Pakistan, there are still serious concerns about local worker's rights. Chinese businesses have come under heavy fire for their worldwide operation's disrespect for worker rights. Concerns about excessive working hours, low wages, and insufficient health and safety safeguards are legitimate in Pakistan, where the majority of CPEC related projects are carried out by Chinese companies (Muhammad Azeem, 2023).

Rights of Labor under CPEC

While CPEC is projected to offer countless job possibilities both for Pakistan and China, major concerns continue around labor rights of the local workers. Chinese companies have been condemned a lot for their disdain for worker rights in their worldwide activates. Concerns about excessive working hours, low wages, and insufficient health and safety safeguards are legitimate in Pakistan, where the majority of

CPEC related projects are carried out by Chinese companies (Muhammad Azeem, 2023).

Conditions of Work under CPEC:

The reports on working conditions at CPEC projects present a mixed image since they lack sufficient transparency. According to certain data, Chinese companies pay higher wages than domestic ones, which can improve local's quality of life (Amjad, 2019). However, issues have been brought up about worker health and safety requirements, especially in energy and construction projects. The CPEC project's lack of transparency prevents policymakers from enhancing worker's working conditions and protecting their rights (Abdul Waheed, 2025).

Implications of Policy:

At the moment, CPEC's working conditions and labor rights do not meet international norms. Ensuring adherence to international labor standards in all CPEC projects is crucial for both Chinese and Pakistani authorities. Additionally, improved working conditions and the inclusion of worker's rights may result from increased labor union participation and transparency in CPEC projects.

Assessing the effects on the environment:

The advantages of CPEC for Pakistan, including Gwadar Port, SEZ's, energy projects, and infrastructural development, are not obscure. To make sure that economic success does not come at the expense of the environment, however, a more thorough analysis is needed to evaluate the project's environmental harm.

Effect on the Ecosystem of the Marine

By 2045, the Gwadar port is expected to have expanded to accommodate 100 berths and handle up to 400 million tons of cargo annually. This is because the port is important for cross-regional connections Marine biodiversity may be harmed by the expansion of shipping and development operations. Because they are disrupting the delicate life and contributing to marine pollution. Further, research is necessary to address the huge rise in

the danger of oil spills, which pose a serious threat to marine ecosystem (Muhammad Nouman Ashraf Khan, 2024).

Wildlife and biodiversity impacts:

The habitats of the animals that live there are frequently fragmented by infrastructure development. Altering their migratory path and making far-flung places more accessible. This result in a rise in illicit wildlife trafficking and robber. As previously stated, a number of CPEC projects pass through environmentally delicate regions, including the Karokaram mountain range, which is home to unique and endangered animals like the Marco Polo Sheep, Bears, IBEX, Markhor and the snow leopard. These project's environmental evaluations frequently overlook the long term and larger ecological context in favor of concentrating on the immediate effects.

Effects on the Environment (Air):

To promote economic activity, a number of SEZ's are established. The majority of power plants rely on coal to meet energy demands, which raises carbon emissions. It is making Pakistan, a country already struggling with poor air quality, more vulnerable to air pollution problems According to research, the carbon emissions from these deiseal, Powered vehicles and coal fired power plants can seriously degrade air quality, endangering human health (Rida Anwar, 2025).

Conclusion:

Although the CPEC's benefits are already widely recognized, this study looks at the project's potential drawbacks in order to maximize its advantages. Minimizing the detrimental socioeconomic effects of CPEC on

Pakistan by conducting a thorough literature analysis and addressing any research gaps. By addressing all of the issues raised in this research, policymakers may endeavor to ensure equitable and sustainable growth in the country. However, as the project is still ongoing, additional problems and effects might occur.

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